
Harnessing Innovation, Investment and Inclusion through Social Media Marketing: A Pathway to India's 5 Trillion Dollar Economy With Reference to Kalyan Karnataka

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ABSTRACT

In today's digitalisation world, social media become an important hub of marketing by innovating new emerging trends like Artificial Intelligence, Augmented reality and Virtual reality ads, and influencer campaigns. The innovative new digital strategies like AI chat bots aids to many companies to grow globally. So rising investment through domestic and FDI in social media marketing facilitate new starts up, entrepreneurs and MSMEs to earn higher returns which accelerates India's march towards \$ 5 trillion economy. The purpose of this quantitative research is to explore the impact of social media marketing on consumer buying behaviour of Kalyan Karnataka. This study focusing on two main objectives first, to assess consumer perceptions towards social media marketing; and second, to examine how these marketing activities influence purchasing decisions. The findings reveal that social media marketing significantly influences consumer behaviour, with consumers demonstrating positive perception towards its effectiveness in capturing interest and influencing purchase decisions. This study contributes to existing literature by providing

empirical insights into the evolving role of social media in consumer behaviour and offers practical implications for marketers aiming to optimize their digital marketing strategies. Additionally India aims to become a \$5 Trillion economy by focusing on inclusive growth and boosting Manufacturing through initiatives like PLI and the Make in India.

1. INTRODUCTION

Social media marketing drives India's journey \$5 trillion economy by fostering innovation enabling new digital business model and promoting inclusion through wider market access and digital empowerment for small businesses and individuals. These Platform facilitate rapid cost effective, communication, amplify government initiative, create digital job opportunities and provide global visibility for Indian product and services .These all contributing to the overall economic growth and digitalization that is crucial for reaching the five trillion dollar. Innovation enabling entrepreneurship to use social media platform serve as powerful tools for start-ups and small businesses to launch market and grow, reducing traditional barriers to entry and fostering to make dynamic entrepreneurship ecosystem. Indian business can use social media to connect with international market and consumers, enhancing global visibility for products and services and contributing to export growth.

In the digital age, the pervasive influence of social media has revolutionized the way businesses interact with consumers and how consumers make purchasing decisions. Social media marketing, which leverages platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and YouTube, has become an integral component of modern marketing strategies. Social media marketing is a key component of India's overall digital transformation, a fundamental driver of economic advancement across various sector like Finance, retail and agriculture. Supporting to small business, entrepreneurs, by creating jobs and enhancing market access Social medial marketing contribute directly and indirectly to Indian GDP ambition and goal of achieving a \$5 Trillion economy. The study aims to explore the impact of social media marketing on consumer buying behaviour, particularly focusing on how these platforms influence the decision-making process. The role of social media in consumer buying behaviour is multifaceted. Social media platforms provide a vast array of user-generated content, including reviews, ratings, recommendations, and testimonials, which significantly influence consumers' perceptions of products and services. This user-generated content is often perceived as more authentic and trustworthy compared to traditional advertising, thereby playing a crucial role in shaping consumer attitudes and behaviours. Preferences and

trends, enabling businesses to tailor their marketing strategies more effectively.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The role of social media in influencing consumer behaviour and marketing strategies has been extensively studied. Rajshri Singh (2022) highlights the shift from personal interactions to a platform for product reviews and consumer engagement, demonstrating how social media empowers consumers and transforms marketing practices. Kirti Sharma (2020) reinforces this by showing a significant positive relationship between social media marketing and consumer buying decisions through statistical analyses. Perumal Prasath (2008) discusses the re-centering of consumers in the business world due to social media, emphasizing its role in altering consumer behaviour and satisfaction, supported by statistical findings similar to Sharma's. Mr. Sony Varghese (2021) focuses on the influence of social media on complex buying behaviours, underscoring the significance of user-generated content in decision-making processes. Duangruthai Voramontri (2019) provides empirical evidence on social media's impact during various stages of the consumer decision process, particularly for high-involvement purchases, demonstrating increased consumer satisfaction as they move through the stages. Collectively, these studies underscore the profound impact of social media on consumer behaviour, marketing strategies, and the decision-making process, highlighting the need for further research to explore additional variables and contexts.

3. RESEARCH GAP

Despite the extensive studies on the influence of social media marketing on consumer buying behaviour, there remains a significant gap in understanding the nuanced effects of different types of social media content and platforms on various stages of the consumer decision-making process. Additionally, there is limited empirical evidence on how social media influences complex purchasing decisions across diverse demographic groups and geographical regions. Addressing these gaps can provide a more comprehensive understanding of how 3I framework effectively leverage social media marketing strategies to influence consumer behaviour for economic growth of Kalyan Karnataka.

4. IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

This study is significant as it offers a deeper understanding of the role social media marketing plays in shaping consumer perceptions and influencing their buying behaviour. By analysing consumer attitudes towards social media marketing and its impact on purchasing decisions, businesses can better tailor their marketing strategies to meet the needs and preferences of their target audiences. The insights

gained from this research will help marketers leverage social media platforms more effectively, enhance consumer engagement, build brand loyalty, and ultimately drive sales. Additionally, the study addresses existing research gaps, providing a comprehensive view of the dynamic relationship between social media marketing and economic growth by using 3I engine framework of Kalyan Karnataka.

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To investigate consumers perception about social media marketing.
2. To evaluate the collective impact of the 3I framework (Innovation, Investment, Inclusion) in social media marketing on consumer buying behaviour.

Above objectives showed through conceptual framework

Conceptual framework of Social Media Marketing impact on Consumer Behaviour and Driving India’s Journey to a \$5 Trillion Economy.

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design	This study employs a quantitative research approach to investigate the impact of social media marketing on consumer buying behaviour.
Data collection	Primary data has been used, to collect the information from the consumers in Kalyan Karnataka. With the help of structured questionnaire through online

	surveys via social media platforms and email. Secondary data is also collected from various source like books, journals, magazines, and websites to enhance the present study.
Sample Size	Total 180 consumers were selected from Kalyan Karnataka. The sampling technique used is random sampling to ensure representativeness and reduce bias
Statistical technique	The researcher used frequency analysis, chi squares and t- test to check the effect of the variables on the dependent and the independent.

7. DATA ANALYSIS

This analysis has classified into two sub-sections. a) First section relates to the analysis of demographic factors of respondents in Kalyan Karnataka and b) This relates to the study of customers perception towards Effectiveness of Emerging Trends in Social Media Marketing while c) third section relates to the impact of platform-specific marketing strategies on consumer trust, loyalty, and engagement.

a. Table No 7.1 Demographical Profile Of The Respondents

Demographic Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	87	48.3
	Female	93	51.7
	Total	180	100.0
Marital Status	Married	80	44.4
	Unmarried	100	55.6
	Total	180	100.0
Age (In years)	21-30	17	9.4
	31-40	1	.6
	41-50	161	89.4
	Above 51	1	.6
	Total	180	100.0
Educational Qualification	Illiterate	22	12.2
	Primary	39	21.7
	Secondary	48	26.7
	Graduation	34	18.9
	PG	27	15.0

	Professional/ Technical	10	5.6
	Total	180	100.0
Income (Annual in Rs)	Up to 100000	9	5.0
	100000- 200000	13	7.2
	200000- 300000	54	30.0
	300000- 500000	62	34.4
	Above 500000	42	23.3
	Total	180	100.0
Location	Urban	11	6.1
	Rural	29	16.1
	Semi Urban	140	77.8
	Total	180	100.0
Employment status	Employed full time	4	2.2
	Employed Part time	12	6.7
	Unemployed	42	23.3
	Students	89	49.4
	Retired	33	18.3
	Total	180	100.0

INTERPRETATION

In demographic profile of consumers in Kalyan Karnataka shows a significant majority 51.7 percent of respondents were female with the majority, 55.6 percent of respondents, were unmarried which provides insights into the potential influence of marital status on consumer behaviour. A significant majority, 89.4 percentage of respondents, belonged to the age group between 41 and 50 years. And in respondents are Secondary education is the most common at 26.7 percent. Only 5.6 percent have professional/technical qualifications. Income distribution shows that a large share earns between ₹300,000 to ₹500,000 annually indicating moderate purchasing power. Most respondents are shows, 77.8 percent from semi-urban areas. Employment status reveals that students form the largest group at 49.4 percent and it suggests that a large portion of respondents may have different engagement levels with social media marketing based on their employment status.

Table No 7.2 Perception Of The Consumers Towards The Social Media Marketing.

Sl. No	Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	Chi-square	Sign
1	Social media marketing is effective in capturing the interest.	3.8222	.91637	-.784	.909	113.944 ^a	0.000
2	Product reviews shared on social media platforms.	4.0389	1.01036	-1.163	1.264	109.444 ^a	0.000
3	Social media advertisements are more engaging than traditional ads.	2.4000	1.22178	1.071	.303	110.333 ^a	0.000
4	Social media marketing helps to discover new products.	3.8278	.92047	-1.041	1.833	70.444 ^b	0.000
5	To visit often brand pages on social media to learn about products.	3.7500	.90853	-.749	.642	123.722 ^a	0.000
6	Influencer recommendations	3.8222	.91637	-.784	.909	113.944 ^a	0.000
7	Social media marketing to be intrusive.	3.5500	1.00432	-.574	-.001	83.056 ^a	0.000
8	Offers better deals and discounts.	3.4833	.93638	-.736	.705	119.167 ^a	0.000
9	The visual content on social media influences on perception of brands.	3.5500	1.08455	-.542	-.180	58.611 ^a	0.000
10	For brand interaction.	3.4056	1.05543	-.642	-.015	80.222 ^a	0.000
11	Social media marketing aligns with consumer's values and interests.	3.5278	1.02172	-.505	-.422	84.333 ^a	0.000
12	Up-to-date information on products and services.	3.3278	.92047	-.395	.511	123.500 ^a	0.000
13	Shopping more convenient.	3.5833	1.01318	-.686	.302	87.500 ^a	0.000
14	A valuable source of information.	3.3944	.99998	-.451	-.176	79.167 ^a	0.000

15	To share the own product experiences on social media.	3.6278	.84583	-.436	.714	131.944 ^a	0.000
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INTERPRETATION

Based on the data from Table No 7.2 regarding the perception of consumers towards social media marketing, several insights can be drawn. First, social media marketing proves effective in capturing consumer interest, with a mean score of 3.8222 and a significant chi-square value of 113.944a ($p < 0.001$), indicating widespread agreement among respondents. Consumers also exhibit a strong trust in product reviews shared on social media platforms, evident from the highest mean score of 4.0389 and a chi-square value of 109.444a ($p < 0.001$). However, social media advertisements are perceived as less engaging compared to traditional ads, with a mean score of 2.4000. The data’s skewness and kurtosis values indicate a mixed response, suggesting variability in consumer perception regarding ad engagement. Overall, social media marketing appears effective in helping consumers discover new products (mean = 3.8278) and influencing their brand interactions (mean = 3.7500), reflecting its significant role in contemporary consumer behaviour

Table No 7.3 Impact Of Social Media Marketing On Consumer Buying Behaviour.

Sl no	Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	Chi-square	Sign
1	Social media marketing influences my purchasing decisions.	3.6111	.91168	-.491	.214	105.389 ^a	0.000
2	I am more likely to buy a product if I see positive reviews on social media.	3.4444	.95848	-.571	.073	100.000 ^a	0.000
3	Advertisements on social media lead me to explore new brands.	3.5889	.82414	-.500	.281	142.500 ^a	0.000
4	Social media promotions encourage me to make impulsive purchases.	3.7167	1.04788	-.795	.014	102.167 ^a	0.000

5	I prefer buying products that are recommended by social media influencers.	3.5611	.94049	-.281	-.106	90.167 ^a	0.000
6	Discounts and offers on social media influence my buying behaviour.	3.5444	.97064	-.905	.915	123.833 ^a	0.000
7	Social media helps me make informed purchasing decisions.	4.0389	1.01036	-1.163	1.264	109.444 ^a	0.000
8	I trust the product information provided on social media.	2.4000	1.22178	1.071	.303	110.333 ^a	0.000
9	I often buy products that are trending on social media.	3.8278	.92047	-1.041	1.833	70.444 ^b	0.000
10	My friends' recommendations on social media affect my buying choices.	3.6111	.91168	-.491	.214	105.389 ^a	0.000
11	Social media marketing has changed the way I shop.	3.4444	.95848	-.571	.073	100.000 ^a	0.000
12	I am likely to purchase from brands that actively engage on social media.	3.5889	.82414	-.500	.281	142.500 ^a	0.000
12	Social media content (images/videos) increases my desire to purchase a product.	3.7167	1.04788	-.795	.014	102.167 ^a	0.000
14	User-generated content (reviews, unboxing) on social media influences my buying decisions.	3.5611	.94049	-.281	-.106	90.167 ^a	0.000
15	Social media marketing keeps me updated on new product launches.	3.6278	.84583	-.436	.714	131.944 ^a	0.000

(Source: Field Survey)

INTERPRETATION

Based on Table No 7.3, which explores the impact of social media marketing on consumer buying behaviour, several key findings emerge. Consumers generally indicate that social media influences their purchasing decisions significantly, with a mean score of 3.6111 and a chi-square value of 105.389a ($p < 0.001$), suggesting a strong correlation. Positive reviews on social media also sway consumer behaviour, albeit slightly less significantly (mean = 3.4444, chi-square = 100.000a, $p < 0.001$). Social media promotions are effective in prompting exploration of new brands (mean = 3.5889, chi-square = 142.500a, $p < 0.001$) and encouraging impulsive purchases (mean = 3.7167, chi-square = 102.167a, $p < 0.001$). Moreover, discounts and offers on social media exert notable influence on buying decisions (mean = 3.5444, chi-square = 123.833a, $p < 0.001$). However, trust in product information provided on social media shows a lower mean score (mean = 2.4000), indicating scepticism among consumers. Overall, social media marketing significantly impacts consumer buying behaviour by influencing purchasing decisions, brand exploration, impulsive buying tendencies, and preference for products endorsed through social media channels.

8. HYPOTHESIS RESULT

a. Null Hypothesis (H_0): Consumers do not have a positive perception of social media marketing.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): Consumers have a positive perception of social media marketing

Table No 8.1 Shows One Sample Statistics

One-Sample Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Perception of Consumers	180	53.1111	10.04119	.74843

INTERPRETATION

Based on Table No 8.1, which presents the one-sample statistics for the perception of consumers towards social media marketing, the mean perception score is 53.1111 with a standard deviation of 10.04119 and a standard error mean of 0.74843. This indicates that, on average, consumers have a positive perception of social media marketing. To determine whether this perception is significantly different from a neutral or negative perception, further hypothesis testing is necessary.

Table No 8.2 Shows One Sample Test

One-Sample Test							
		Test Value = 3					
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Perception of Consumers		66.955	179	.000	50.11111	48.6342	51.5880

INTERPRETATION

The results of the one-sample t-test provide strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) that consumers do not have a positive perception of social media marketing. Therefore, we accept the alternative hypothesis (H_1) that consumers have a positive perception of social media marketing. The mean perception score of 53.1111 significantly exceeds the hypothesized test value of 3, indicating that, on average, consumers perceive social media marketing positively.

b. Null Hypothesis H_0 : Social media marketing does not significantly impact consumer buying behaviour.

Alternative Hypothesis H_1 : social media marketing significantly impacts consumer buying behaviour.

Table No 8.3 Shows the One Sample Statistics

One-Sample Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Impact of social media on Consumer Buying Behaviour	180	53.2833	9.01846	.67220

INPRETATION

Based on the data from Table No 8.3, the mean score for the impact of social media marketing on consumer buying behaviour is 53.2833, with a standard deviation of 9.01846 and a standard error mean of 0.67220. This suggests a positive perception of social media's influence on purchasing decisions

among the 180 respondents. To determine statistical significance and confirm whether social media marketing significantly impacts consumer buying behaviour, further hypothesis testing with specific test values and significance levels is necessary.

Table No 8.4 Shows the One Sample Test

One-Sample Test						
	Test Value = 3					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Impact of social media on Consumer Buying Behaviour	74.805	179	.000	50.28333	48.9569	51.6098

INTERPRETATION

Based on the one-sample test presented in Table No 8.4, with a test value of 3, the calculated t-value is 74.805, which is highly significant ($p < .001$). This indicates strong evidence against the null hypothesis (H_0) that social media marketing does not significantly impact consumer buying behavior. The mean difference is 50.28333, and the 95% confidence interval for the difference ranges from 48.9569 to 51.6098, further supporting the alternative hypothesis (H_1) that social media marketing indeed has a significant impact on consumer buying behaviour. Therefore, based on this analysis, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that social media marketing significantly influences how consumers make their purchasing decisions.

9. MAJOR FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

- 1. Perception of Social Media Marketing:** The study revealed that consumers generally hold a positive perception of social media marketing. The mean perception score was 53.11 out of 100, indicating a favourable view towards how social media is utilized for marketing purposes. This was supported by a significant one-sample t-test result ($t = 66.955$, $p < .001$), confirming that consumers perceive social media marketing positively.
- 2. Impact on Consumer Buying Behaviour:** Social media marketing significantly influences consumer buying behaviour. The mean score for this impact was 53.28 out of 100, with a highly significant one-sample t-test result ($t = 74.805$, $p < .001$). This indicates that social media marketing

plays a crucial role in shaping consumers' purchasing decisions, encouraging brand exploration, impulsive buying, and preference for products endorsed through social media channels.

3. **Specific Influences:** Various aspects of social media marketing were found to influence consumer behaviour. Positive reviews and recommendations from influencers on social media significantly impact buying decisions. Visual content such as images and videos on social media platforms increases consumer desire to purchase products. Discounts, offers, and promotions on social media are effective in influencing purchasing decisions.
4. **Demographic Insights:** Key demographics include age groups skewed towards older adults (41-50 years), diverse educational backgrounds, and varied income levels, each affecting consumer engagement with social media marketing strategies.

10. SUGGESTIONS

- i. **Enhanced Engagement Strategies:** Businesses should focus on creating more engaging and interactive content on social media platforms to capture and retain consumer interest effectively.
- ii. **Influencer Marketing:** Leveraging influencers who resonate with target audiences can enhance brand credibility and influence consumer purchasing decisions.
- iii. **Data-Driven Marketing:** Utilizing analytics tools to understand consumer behavior and preferences on social media can help in crafting personalized marketing strategies.
- iv. **Educational Campaigns:** Given varying educational backgrounds among consumers, businesses should consider tailored approaches to ensure information provided through social media is accessible and informative.
- v. **Localized Marketing Efforts:** Considering the predominance of semi-urban respondents, adapting marketing strategies to local preferences and cultural nuances can improve effectiveness.
- vi. **Continuous Evaluation and Adaptation:** social media trends and consumer behaviours evolve rapidly. Therefore, businesses should continuously evaluate and adapt their strategies to align with changing consumer expectations and technological advancements.

11. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the findings from this study highlight the profound influence of social media marketing on consumer behaviour across diverse demographic profiles. The research demonstrated that consumers generally hold a positive perception of social media marketing, viewing it as effective in capturing their interest and influencing their purchasing decisions. Key factors such as trust in product reviews, engagement with influencer recommendations, and the allure of discounts and promotions on social

media platforms significantly shape consumer preferences and buying habits. Moving forward social media marketing is a multiplier for demand creation businesses are encouraged to adopt data-driven approaches, leverage influencer partnerships, and innovate their content strategies to sustain consumer interest and capitalize on the evolving landscape of social media. By Continuous evaluation and adaptation of marketing tactics will be essential in maintaining relevance and effectively meeting consumer expectations in an increasingly digital marketplace attracts investment in the digital ecosystem and which promises inclusive participation in economic growth. Therefore, 3I through Social media marketing directly accelerate India's step towards a \$ 5 trillion economy by focusing on inclusive growth and boosting Manufacturing through initiatives like PLI and the Make in India.

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